

**ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ҲУҚУҚНИ
МУҲОФАЗА ҚИЛИШ АКАДЕМИЯСИ**

**РАҚАМЛИ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ ДАВРИДА
ҲУҚУҚНИ МУҲОФАЗА ҚИЛИШ СОҲАСИДАГИ
ЗАМОНАВИЙ ЧАҚИРИҚ ВА ТАҲДИДЛАР**

мавзусидаги халқаро илмий-амалий
конференция материаллари

Т Ў П Л А М И

1-ЖИЛД

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1-ЖИЛД**

С Б О Р Н И К

материалов международной научно-практической конференции на
тему:

**СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ УГРОЗЫ И ВЫЗОВЫ В
ПРАВООХРАНИТЕЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В
ЭПОХУ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ
1-ТОМ**

**MODERN THREATS AND CHALLENGES IN LAW
ENFORCEMENT IN THE ERA OF DIGITAL
TRANSFORMATION**

Materials of the international conference Collection
Volume I

Toshkent -2025

the activities of law enforcement agencies in the era of digital technologies.

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**THE LEGAL FOUNDATIONS OF COMBATING CORRUPTION
AND BUREAUCRATIC OBSTACLES IN SCIENTIFIC
ACTIVITY
(the case of Uzbekistan)**

Science is the driving force behind the development of the state and society. The advancement of science is considered the foundation of the future and the guarantee of progress. Since 2016, Uzbekistan has paid significant attention to the development of science and education, the enhancement of the effectiveness of scientific research activities, and the support of innovative ideas. As a result of the large-scale open and fair policy pursued by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, it has been repeatedly emphasized that all reforms are being carried out based on scientific approaches.

In this regard, it is essential to combat any corrupt and bureaucratic factors that hinder the development of science. This requires analyzing and improving Uzbekistan's national legislation based on international documents and standards.

In particular, among international documents, the United Nations Convention against Corruption (adopted by the UN General Assembly on October 31, 2003) serves as the main legal instrument that fully reveals the essence of corruption and outlines measures to combat it. It is crucial for all states to work together with the international community to implement anti-corruption measures. In this regard, the Convention provides guidelines for further improving national legislation.

Although the issue of corruption has been on the government's agenda as one of the most pressing matters since the early years of Uzbekistan's independence, its legal foundations had not been fully established.

In our opinion, the formation of the legal and institutional foundations for combating corruption in Uzbekistan can be divided into two distinct periods. The first period spans from 1991 to 2017, while the second period covers the time from 2017 to the present day.

During the first period, the primary focus was on strengthening punitive measures against corruption-related crimes and addressing their consequences.

In contrast, starting from 2017, the second period has been characterized by a shift toward aligning with international anti-corruption standards, emphasizing the prevention of corruption and eliminating its root causes, with particular attention given to preventive measures.

The first legal step in combating corruption in Uzbekistan can be considered the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers №103, dated March 6, 1992, "On the Approval of the List of Officials Prohibited from Engaging in Entrepreneurial Activities."

In 2008, Uzbekistan acceded to the United Nations Convention against Corruption and assumed the obligation to comply with the requirements established by this convention.

Combating corruption, including the prevention of bureaucracy in scientific activity, is no exception. Accordingly, it is necessary to legally regulate this sphere in order to prevent corruption and bureaucracy, timely detect and eliminate corrupt offenses, and apply legal measures against corruption-related violations.

In particular, the legal foundations for combating corruption and bureaucratic obstacles in scientific activity are formed by international documents, laws and by-laws (including laws, resolutions of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis, decrees and resolutions of the President, resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers, as well as orders and resolutions of ministries, state committees, and agencies), and internal departmental regulatory documents issued by ministries and other bodies.

Accordingly, we have attempted to analyze the legal foundations for combating corruption and bureaucratic obstacles in scientific activity based on international documents and standards, national regulatory legal acts (laws and by-laws), and internal departmental regulations.

As rightly noted by some authors, it is advisable to regulate the key legal foundations for combating and preventing corruption through both international legal instruments and national legislation. At the same time, it is important to take into account that the emergence, development causes, and conditions of corruption may vary depending on the level of socio-economic changes in each country. Therefore, since there are no universally applicable procedures for preventing and combating corruption, developing universal administrative and legal mechanisms in this area remains a complex task.

Countries around the world and leading international organizations have been adopting conventions, pacts, and other types of international documents aimed at combating and preventing corruption across all sectors. Today, the key normative legal foundations for combating and preventing corruption are reflected in several international legal instruments.

With the ratification of the United Nations Convention against Corruption by the Republic of Uzbekistan, the country has undertaken international obligations to combat and prevent corruption.

For this purpose, Uzbekistan has also ratified the Charter of the Islamic Organization for Education, Science, and Culture (Baku, November 26, 2015).

It is worth noting that in Uzbekistan, comprehensive and systematic measures are being implemented to introduce a system based on advanced international standards for combating and preventing corruption, as well as preventing the commission of such crimes. These measures aim to eliminate the problems that give rise to corruption across all areas of state and public life, including the field of public education.

Since the aforementioned international documents have created obligations for Uzbekistan, continuous efforts have been made to improve the national regulatory framework for combating corruption. The enactment of the Law on Combating Corruption, along with the adoption of various by-laws, has contributed to the formation of a solid legal foundation in this field.

In particular, on January 3, 2017, the Law “On fighting corruption” was adopted. This law defines the main directions of state policy in the fight against corruption, outlines measures for the prevention of corruption in this field, establishes procedures for the detection and suppression of corruption-related offenses, and sets the framework for international cooperation in this regard.

As rightly noted by our national scholars, this law has created a legal mechanism for combating corruption, making it an important normative legal document that concerns the fate of the state and society, the future of the people, and every citizen.

In our country, a comprehensive legislative system for combating corruption has been established. Numerous legal documents can be cited in this regard. However, when it comes to combating corruption specifically in the field of scientific activity, the following key legislative acts are of particular importance: the Law " On fighting corruption" (2017), the Law " On state civil service" (2022), as well as several presidential decrees, including: "On measures to further improve the anti-corruption system in the Republic of Uzbekistan" (2019), "On approval of the Concept for the Development of the Public Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" (2019), "On approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" (2019), "On approval of the concept of development of science until 2030" (2020), "On measures to create an environment of zero-tolerance against corruption, to drastically reduce corruption factors in state and community management, and to expand public participation in this" (2021), "On approval of the Regulation on the procedure for organizing training on the electronic platform "Virtual Anti-Corruption Academy" (2024), "On the measures to effectively organize the implementation of priority tasks for the further improvement of the anti-corruption system" (2025).

These and similar normative legal acts play a significant role in regulating anti-corruption efforts in the scientific sphere.

The relevance of researching manifestations of corruption in the scientific sector is directly linked to the growing impact of science on the socio-economic development of society and the need to ensure the reliability of scientific results as the foundation for innovative development. This issue is particularly important in the context of the modernization of the scientific and educational system in Uzbekistan, where a large-scale program of reforms in science and higher education has been implemented in recent years.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan № PQ-2909 "On measures for further development of the higher education system" and the Resolution №PQ-3775 "On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in comprehensive reforms

implemented in the country” special attention has been given to improving the quality of scientific research and integrating it into the international scientific arena.

One of the most widespread forms of corruption in the scientific sphere is the misuse and inefficient utilization of funds allocated for research projects. As some scholars have rightly pointed out, “the lack of transparency in the procedures for distributing grants and subsidies creates favorable conditions for lobbying the interests of certain scientific groups and fields, which are not always justified from a scientific significance perspective” (Yurevich A.V.).

This leads to the irrational use of limited resources allocated for scientific research and, ultimately, to a decrease in the overall effectiveness of scientific activity. In Uzbekistan, this issue has become particularly relevant in light of the increased state funding for science within the framework of the State Program for the Implementation of the Action Strategy.

A significant step in this direction was the establishment of the Agency for Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017, as well as the adoption of the Law “About science and scientific activity” in 2019, which provided the legal foundation for improving the mechanisms of financing scientific research.

Based on Uzbekistan’s experience in reforming the science funding system, project-targeted financing methods have been introduced in recent years, and work is underway to establish independent expert councils. According to the Agency for Innovative Development, the share of competitive (grant-based) funding in the total budget allocated for science increased from 10% (percent) in 2020 to 35% (percent) in 2024.

However, it is necessary to address some pressing issues.

In particular, the evaluation of scientific activity effectiveness has given rise to new forms of corruption related to publication practices. Studies indicate that an entire industry of so-called “**predatory**” journals has emerged, ready to publish articles without proper peer review in exchange for a certain fee. Such practices not only discredit the system of scientific communication but also contribute to the spread of unreliable information presented as scientific knowledge.

One especially concerning phenomenon is “**compulsory co-authorship**”, where officials, without actual participation in research, use their administrative resources to include themselves in the list of authors of scientific publications.

In Uzbekistan's scientific and educational system, issues of publication ethics have become particularly relevant in recent years due to the introduction of publication activity indicators in the systems for evaluating the effectiveness of scientific activity and attesting scientific and pedagogical personnel. According to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers dated July 19, 2019, "On the improvement of the targeted training system of highly qualified scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel" having publications in journals indexed in international databases has become a mandatory requirement for candidates for academic degrees.

According to research conducted by a group of scholars from the National University of Uzbekistan, approximately 30% (percent) of publications by Uzbek authors in foreign journals between 2020 and 2022 were published in journals exhibiting characteristics of "predatory" publishing.

The practice of "compulsory co-authorship" also remains widespread in Uzbekistan's scientific and educational institutions. A sociological survey conducted in 2024 by the "Ijtimoiy fikr" Center for the Study of Public Opinion showed that 23% (percent) of scientific workers and university teachers surveyed had encountered situations where they were forced to include various levels of managers, who did not participate in the research, as co-authors of scientific publications.

The analysis of corruption and bureaucratic manifestations in scientific activity highlights the necessity of a comprehensive approach to solving these issues. Eliminating negative trends requires not only the improvement of the regulatory and administrative mechanisms but also the active involvement of the scientific community in shaping and upholding high ethical standards.

Based on the analysis of the legal foundations for combating and preventing corruption and bureaucracy in scientific activity, the following conclusions can be drawn:

First, developing any sector without proper legal regulation presents significant challenges. In this context, organizing anti-corruption measures and combating corruption is inherently linked to creating the legal foundations that regulate the sector.

Second, in today's era of globalization, the rapid spread of corruption worldwide necessitates the development of national legal norms for preventing and combating corruption in alignment with international legal standards and norms.

Third, the legal foundations for preventing corruption and combating bureaucracy in scientific activity are based on universally recognized international documents and standards, as well as key and fundamental normative legal acts within the national legal system.

Fourth, anti-corruption and anti-bureaucratic measures in scientific activity are regulated through laws, by-laws, resolutions of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovation, and internal departmental documents. This regulation is implemented through the adoption of charters, instructions, rules, regulations, concepts, strategies, programs (roadmaps), and other related documents aimed at preventing corruption and combating bureaucracy in this field.

In conclusion, considering the severe consequences of corruption for state and societal development, preventing corruption in all sectors, including scientific activity, holds crucial importance today. The creation of legal mechanisms aimed at regulating this field plays a vital role in preventing corruption and combating bureaucracy.

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OPTIONAL ELEMENTS OF THE CRIME SUBJECT: CONCEPT AND ESSENCE

***Abstract:** This article provides a comprehensive theoretical and practical analysis of the concept and legal nature of the elements of a crime. It examines the core components of a crime – the object, the subject, as well as the objective and subjective elements – with particular attention to their legal significance. Special emphasis is placed on the optional characteristics of the crime subject, and the concept of a "special subject" is thoroughly explored. The study conducts a comparative analysis of the criminal legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Federal Republic of Germany, and the Republic of Belarus, offering a critical assessment of existing approaches within the national legal framework. The conclusion substantiates the need for further clarification of the provisions of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan concerning the structure and elements of a crime.*

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Ўзбекистон Республикаси Хуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш академиясига

Олий аттестация комиссияси Сизнинг 2025 йил 3 июндаги 30/5-89625/25-сонли хатингизга жавобан ОАК Раёсатининг 2025 йил 13 июндаги 371/6-сон қарори асосида Ўзбекистон Республикаси Хуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш академияси ташкил этилганлиги муносабати 2025 йилнинг 19-20 июнь кунлари (Тошкент ш.) “Рақамли трансформация даврида хуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш фаолияти соҳасида замонавий чақириқлар ва таҳдидлар” мавзусида ўтказиладиган халқаро илмий-амалий конференция тўпламида чоп этилган (инглиз тилида) илмий мақолалар (маъруза ва тезислар бундан мустасно) диссертация асосий илмий натижаларини чоп этиш тавсия этилган илмий нашрлар рўйхатига киритилган хорижий илмий нашрларда чоп этилган хорижий илмий нашрларда чоп этилган илмий мақола сифатида қабул қилинишини маълум қилади.

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1-ТОМ

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